

RESEARCH INTO THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE INDEPENDENCE YEARS OF THE CITY OF NUKUS AND THE WAYS OF ITS FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation: The article scientifically describes the practical experience, achievements and shortcomings of the city of Nukus in the field of architecture and urban planning during the years of independence, and develops proposals and comments on the effective use of this scientific heritage for the future development of modern architecture.

Keywords: City, building materials, fortification, landscaping, education, alley, landscaping, square, construction.

The city of Nukus is located in the central part of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. On the Right Bank of the Amu Darya. At an altitude of 76 meters above sea level. Surrounded by the Kyzylkum Desert to the south and East. In the north, it is adjacent to the Amudarya Delta. The Kizketgan canal crosses the city.

The city's climate is Continental, with dry summers and hot summers. During the winter, short-term severe frosts occur.

The total area of the city of Nukus is 200 sq.km, more than, the population is 300 thousand people. On November 12, 1930, it was decided to make the city of Nukus the capital of the Republic. In 1939, the Republican administration moved

to the city of Nukus. More than 100 industrial enterprises, joint ventures in cooperation with the developed countries of Jahan operate in the city. The industries of metalworking, building materials, food, light industry, woodworking and printing are in a civilized spring. They have established effective cooperation relations with partners in Germany, England, Japan, Russia, Korea, China, Canada, Turkey, Saudi Arabia, Ukraine.

The first people in the territory of the current city of Nukus began to live in the 4th - 3rd centuries BC. The history of Shurcha Castle, which occupies the central part of the city's territory, covers a period of more than 2000 years. Archaeological studies have shown that life existed in Shurcha Kal between the 4th century BC and the 4th century AD, it was one of the fortification forts in the north-west of the ancient Khorezm state, a citadel that guarded the border and controlled the waterway through the Amu Darya.

For 30 years, our Republic has been following the paths of Democratic, socio-spiritual life, political, ideological and economic. The city of Nukus is also going through such a complex and responsible path. Our city celebrated its multi-year birthday wedding in honor. For a city that is so old, many years of tarakkiyot it is not a period of utter reverence in the face of ancient history. Brother, during these years, the city of Nukus has done a remarkable, remarkable and great job in its social material and cultural life. I, who was the first president of our Republic from the first days of independence. A.Karimov paid great attention to the development of socio-economic, spiritual and educational, urban planning and architecture of the capital of our country Tashkent and other prestigious and historical cities. One such city where the eyes of our first president fell was Nukus. In the city of Nukus, work in the area we are talking about was carried out in several directions.

The first of them was the development of urban streets, squares, its most influential components in accordance with the requirements of our independence,

the ideology of independence, the domestic lifestyle of the population and the market economy.

The second direction was the viewing and placement of household-cultural living, educational-Educational, Scientific and economic development, industrial and industrial market and trade objects based on new social principles throughout the territory of the city.

The third direction was the work in the field of repair, restoration, adaptation of the historical part of the city, architectural monuments in it to the goals of modern social and tourism, and in this way their preservation for future generations, taking into account the historicity and universal status of the city of Nukus.

And the work on **the fourth direction** was aimed at improving the recreation of the population, the climate, ecology and landscape of the city, that is, the improvement of the external open environment, the organization and formation of greenery, flower beds, new gardens, and parks, alleys.

And **the fifth line** is aimed at improving the municipal life of the city, improving and equipping of the architecture, practically revitalizing these works.

As you know, all these directions are associated with architecture and urban planning, as well as urban construction work. It was for this purpose that the general urban planning plan for the development of the city of Nukus for 2025 was developed and approved and put into operation during the years of Independence. It reflects the work in all of the above directions.

1. Experiments in the field of regulation of city streets, squares, its most influential components in accordance with the development of our independence, the ideology of independence, the domestic lifestyle of the population and the requirements of the market economy;

2. Domestic and cultural life, education, science and economic development, construction, placement of industrial and production facilities and their

architecture, based on the principles of new social development throughout the territory of the city;

3. Experiments on the repair, restoration of existing architectural monuments in the city of Nukus and the Republic of Karakalpak, their adaptation to modern social and tourism goals;

4. Aimed at improving the recreation, urban climate, ecology and landscape of the population, that is, landscaping, landscaping, flower arrangement, new garden, and the organization and formation of parks, alleys.

In the years of independence of Nukus city - carefully enhancing the created architectural structures and complexes, urban planning ensembles and creative work, we note the harmony of the majestic and natural landscapes inherent in them, the orastness in their environment, consistent architectural order, high architectural feelings of folk applied art. Unfortunately, these important and high architectural qualities are now lacking in the atmosphere of buildings and structures that are being created in some district centers and villages. We believe that our Ring of material cultural values, reflected in the extensive creative work carried out during the years of independence, will lead our thinking towards new opportunities.

Today, to our compatriots who have made our Nukus known to the world with their intelligence and perseverance, who have become true architects of the socio-spiritual, cultural-educational, economic, educational and creative work of our city, we are also proud to tell our thanks.

The city rightfully honors its achievements in the field of construction and creativity. Construction Enterprises built dozens of magnificent , modern administrative and residential buildings in the city, extensive and smooth roads were built. The structures are being built in harmony with modernity with examples of folk traditional architecture. Building-woodworking materials, however, are being processed here itself.

At present, a transport network has been formed in Nukus that meets all the requirements. All motor vehicles are equipped with modern cars. Especially long-distance travel is in rapid development.

Updates to the railway network have become one of the fruits of independence. As a result of the construction of the uchkuduk-Nukus railway network, the distance between Tashkent and Nukus became closer. At the same time, it was made possible to carry out train services only on the territory of Uzbekistan. The economic and social effects of this are incomparable.

The conclusion draws from all this is that, based on the socio - economic capabilities of the city of Nukus, today's generation is laying the foundation brick, which is worthy of the future development of our city. Undoubtedly, this is only a prelude to the great creative work that will be in the future. This means that today's generation is not limited to the preservation of the great heritage left by our grandfathers, the honor from its height and priceless. They are adding worthy masterpieces next to these masterpieces. They will enrich the treasure of our architectural and spiritual heritage, and this intensity, passion, creativity will never end, will flare up and develop more and more.

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